

SCIENTIFIC-PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPMENT OF HERMENEUTIC COMPETENCE OF FUTURE MUSIC EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract: The article presents three components of the educational process: a competency-based approach to the organization of the educational process, focusing on its result; systematic-active approach to systematization of students' educational activities; A person-oriented approach to the programming of "student-teacher" relations, which implies subject-subject relations affecting the formation of hermeneutic competence, is analyzed.

Key words: pedagogue, professional competence, classification, improvement, competence, hermeneutic competence.

A musician is a creative person, he is both an archer and an adjuster of the emotional atmosphere in a particular environment and in society as a whole, therefore his sensitivity, the ability to understand and empathize, his emotional connection with the composer. the listener is especially important.

In our opinion, the development of hermeneutic competence is of particular importance for a professional musician. Hermeneutics, with its analytical apparatus, opens one of the effective ways of solving pedagogical problems in the field of music education.

In recent years, educational standards have focused not only on the process, but also on the results of education, on the formation of a self-satisfied specialist who is ready for professional activity, can adapt to society and benefit society.

This explains why the anthropocentric paradigm of education is developing in the 20th and 21st centuries (B. Battelheim, V. S. Bibler, O. F. Bollnow, D. Derbolaf, I. P. Ivanov, B. V. Kulikov, S. Yu. Kurganov, A. Niller, D. D., K. Rogers, G. Roth, etc.), in the center of which the student's personality, its formation, development is improved "by affecting the deeper need-emotional sphere". Thus, the student is introduced to the process of "self-building" of his personality, self-management and self-planning of his educational activities. In our opinion, A.V. Khutorsky's thoughts on human-friendly education are close to this direction of education.

The issue of competences has been repeatedly discussed by the most prominent scientists - psychologists, pedagogues, methodologists (A.V. Barannikov, E.A. Bystrova, V.A. Bolotov, V.P. Borisenkov, A. Dakhin, G.S. Zavatskaya, I.A. Zimnyaya,

G.A. Larionova, O.E. Lebedev, A.F. Prisajnyaya , L.V.Savelyeva, G.Selevko, I.S.Sergeev, B.V.Serikov, M.A.Kholodnaya, A.V.Khutorskoy, T.I.Shamova, N.M.Shansky and others) were researched.

Implementation of this model of education in modern pedagogy is carried out in three components of the educational process, in three methodological approaches:

1) a competence-based approach to the organization of the educational process, focusing on its results;

2) systematic-active approach to systematization of students' educational activities;

3) a person-oriented approach to programming "student-teacher" relationships, which implies subject-subject relationships.

To be competent means to be able to use the knowledge and experience gained in a specific situation (to be capable), that is, to have the main indicators of professional skills. Competence is the degree of possession of professional qualities, the ability of a certain person to perform certain professional actions.

Determining that the graduate has competence, that is, what he is capable of, what type of activity he has mastered, and what he is ready for is called a competency-based approach.

For musicians and music teachers, in our opinion, first of all, the following are relevant: a) social competencies, which imply the ability to find one's place in society; b) competences related to the life of a multinational society (therefore, the education of tolerance plays an important role); c) communicative competences related to mastering oral and written communication (including mastering one and preferably several foreign languages); d) information competences related to mastering new information technologies using computer technologies; e) Competencies related to the ability to continuously and consistently learn throughout a person's life. These core competencies are cross-functional in nature.

The introduction of hermeneutics into pedagogy marked the 20th century. Hermeneutics offered a methodology for understanding, and the implementation of this methodology cannot but help to improve the entire process of training a professional of any profile. Even F. Schleiermacher (1804-1834) said that correct understanding is understanding according to a certain technique. This concept needs to be learned as one learns a craft. Understanding is a necessary condition and integral part of human education. This is the basis of education. Thus, the learning goal can be defined as moving from

misunderstanding to understanding. The subject of interpretation becomes "transition from vague infinity to certainty".

The hermeneutic approach is based on the humanist philosophy of N.A. Berdyaev, A.F. Losev, V.S. Solovyov, G.G. Shpet, P.A. Florensky, F. Schleiermacher, V. Dilthey, M. Heidegger, H.G. Gadamer, P. Ricoeur.

The works of the following scientists related to general and musical pedagogy played an important role in the search for a theoretical justification of the hermeneutic approach in music pedagogy: E.B. Rajnikova and others.

Based on V. Dilthey's theory of hermeneutic pedagogy, he calls the things reflected in the modern ones as general cultural and professional competences, and in our opinion, it implies the ability to implement music education as a result of the hermeneutic analysis of the musical text. The penetration of hermeneutics into the field of musical creation allowed a deeper and adequate analysis of the musical text.

As S. Belyaeva-Ekzemplyarskaya noted, musical hermeneutics appeared in the works of G. Krechmar and was improved in debates with K. Dalhaus, A. Shering and other musicians, music teachers and critics.

A. Bikbaeva, M. Barnfeld, Y. N. Bychkov, Y. Zakharov, L. P. Kazantseva, M. G. Karpichev, I. E. Molostvova, S. M. Filippov, V. N. Kholopova, T. V. Cherednichenko, V. I. Shakhovskiy, V. P. Shestakov and others engaged.

Hermeneutic competence requires consideration of its four components:

1) understanding, penetrating the content, idea, author's purpose of the work, getting used to the inner world of the author (divination);

2) the ability to use the "hermeneutic circle" technique (F.D. Schleiermacher), to be able to see the "structure" of the musical text (P. Ricoeur), the expression of the "internal dynamics" that guided this structure in it, every component of the work - tact, phrase and the ability to determine the purpose of others, its role in the overall structure of work; the ability to reveal the author's way of realizing the idea of the work in every smallest particle and in the entire text;

3) connecting the content of the work with contemporary experience (J. Habermas), seeing the generation of new meanings in dialogue with tradition (P. Ricoeur, G.G. Gadamer);

4) to know the information from the biography of the author of the text, to study his environment, education and the field of professional communication.

A.F. Zokirova considers the hermeneutic approach to training a teacher, in our case a musician, and puts forward the principle of harmonizing

epistemological and ontological plans for understanding the content embodied in texts, rational explanation and synthesis of intuitive understanding.

The activity approach is based on the belief that a person develops and is formed only in the process of his activity. This is how freedom of choice is realized, learning motivation increases and interests develop. In the interaction with the outside world, the activity of the individual is manifested, new needs and motives are formed. The activity approach involves pedagogical interaction, the establishment of subject-subject relationships, which is consistent with the person-centered approach.

For the activity approach, the focus should be on learning outcomes, growth and active use of creative potential. In this case, activity motivation and activation of creative potential are of particular importance.

Activity is not only physical movements, not only work, technology, but also mental activity, only then can education take human form. The basis of educational activity is creative activity, its content is its productivity, the product of activity - a new thing created in its process - is the result of activity. The activity always involves creating something new - a spoken text, a new interpretation of a musical text, etc.

The content and importance of the activity approach is that the student:

1) not only receives ready-made knowledge, but also determines it himself; 2) learns new things while performing professionally useful actions and operations; 3) realizes his creative potential; 4) independently chooses methods of activity to achieve the set goal - cognitive, research, creative; 5) aims at reflective activity, learns to realistically evaluate the results of his activity. And most importantly, this approach helps a person to understand himself in the process of educational activities.

It can be seen that these requirements of modern pedagogy fully correspond to the ideas of the hermeneutic approach and the ideas of forming the hermeneutic competence of the future musician and teacher.

Person-oriented education is learning that creates conditions for the full manifestation, formation and development of the individual in the educational process, which means recognition of the uniqueness of each student by the teacher (N.A. Alekseev, E.V.Bondarevskaya, A.S.Granitskaya, L.M.Kustov, N.V.Kustova, G.Selevko, V.V.Serikov, A.V.Khutorskoi, N.E.Shchurkova, I.S.Yakimanskaya and others), his "self-awareness" rights (A.Maslow) target the personality of a musician allows to form.

The main goal of the person-oriented approach is the student himself, his culture and creativity. This approach includes friendly, respectful communication with each other, acceptance of different points of view and positions, positive attitude. Person-oriented education creates conditions for the subject's full formation and development in the process of understanding the worldview of the socio-cultural community, because:

1) initially defines the student as an active subject of educational activity, gives him the opportunity to ask questions without limiting his activity or initiative;

2) creates conditions for the development of personal qualities, such as the ability to develop creative potential and cognitive interest;

3) relies on the subjective experience of the student, thereby updating previously acquired knowledge, skills and abilities;

4) takes into account the individual psychological characteristics of each student as much as possible;

5) gives the student the opportunity to independently choose the optimal strategies for mastering the educational material.

The selected approach focuses on the development of the creative potential of a person, involving him in independent knowledge activities in the forms of individual, group and collective work, and requires the introduction of ethno-cultural material into the educational process in a multicultural society and world, taking into account the existence of the student. .

A person-oriented approach allows solving the problem of mutual understanding between the subjects of the pedagogical process, defines the basis for the formation of the teacher's professional competence, and helps to improve the mechanism of meaning formation in the process of acquiring humanitarian knowledge in the future. A person-oriented approach to teaching is inextricably linked with a competency-based approach and a hermeneutic approach in organizing the training of musicians and teachers.

A.F. Zokirova (2001) emphasizes that the hermeneutic approach is of particular importance in the professional training of a future teacher, who is not only ready to implement given scientific projects in the modern socio-cultural environment, but also the textual semantic field of innovative search in life, social interpret the order, connect the priorities of social values and norms with common cultural and personal meanings, avoid stereotyping schematization and personalization of knowledge about the person.

The formation of hermeneutic competence allows to direct the whole process to a holistic understanding of cultural, universal human values.

Person-oriented and activity-based approaches create conditions for students' self-development and formation of the most relevant skills in the period of changes and social cataclysms in choosing the type of activity and social roles.

All of the above leads us to the idea that the curriculum for training a musician-performer and teacher should include a special subject that focuses the attention of teachers and students on the hermeneutic approach.

Of course, the formation of hermeneutic competence is not a one-time or even one-semester process, it should be continuous throughout the entire study at the university. Hermeneutic competence is formed in the process of adding general cultural competences, because it lies in the understanding of social movements, trends and traditions, in familiarization with common cultural values and historical facts. Hermeneutic competence is formed in the process of mastering general professional sciences, as they provide a basis for understanding music and a demanding, but at the same time respectful attitude towards it, and provide an understanding of the general process of the development of musical thinking from ancient times to the present day.

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